

MASTER PLAN FOR DELHI – BRIEF

(MPD 2041)

Author: Deepak Kumar Chaurasia

Chandigarh University

INTRODUCTION

The main objective behind this master plan is to achieve development strategically, the authorities will assess the current situation and make the plans according to it. This plan will include several agencies such as service providers, regulators, other concerned authorities, also involving the Central Government.

This sort of development model has been followed in Delhi since 1962, under the Delhi Development Act of 1957 (DDA). Initially, it was started in 1962, followed by the years 2001 and 2021. The master plan was prepared for a tenure of 20 years. It focussed on several aspects which required attention and improvement.

BIFURCATION OF MPD 2041

The master plan for Delhi has been bifurcated into two volumes. The first volume provides an overview of Delhi's present condition and contains the vision, objectives of MPD 2041. This volume has been further bifurcated into Six Sections, which cover all the major areas such as Transport and Mobility, Heritage, Shelter and Social Infrastructure and Physical Infrastructure, Environment, Economy (it covers the Government offices, trade & commerce wholesale trade, industry).

The Second Volume contains the plan for evaluation and monitoring, strategy, and Action Plan. It is also further bifurcated into three sections. All the major strategies and detailed provisions are there in the first section of Volume 2, MPD 2041. It covers the major area of development, covering both the green and brown fields.

AREA OF MAJOR CONCERN

The draft of MPD 2041 released on the official website of the Delhi Government¹, states the focus area to work upon, some of them are as follows:

1. Water: Water Scarcity in Delhi is a big issue Infront of Delhi Development Authorities, the main reason behind the water scarcity is the lack of reuse strategy and conservation. This can have a major implication on the growth and development of Delhi.
2. Environment: Delhi is already tackling the air & noise pollution issues. The Yamuna is also polluted at a vast level. The quality of greens also needs to be improved in some of the places. This proves to be threatening for the environment and the health of the citizens.
3. Economic Potential: Delhi, if full potential is realized, will convert Delhi into Economic Hub. Special emphasis to be given on health and Higher Education, start-ups m innovation. Providing a business-friendly environment and ease of doing business. Other sectors such as tourism, specialized trade, etc. to be promoted.

There are many other points which are widely covered in the MPD 2041 draft.

CONCLUSION & PERSONAL OBSERVATIONS

The Master plan of Delhi is a comprehensive development strategy, which focuses on every major sector/field. It carries a vision, that is “*Delhi Vision 2041*”, and the vision is to “*Foster a Sustainable, Liveable and Vibrant Delhi*”. The Delhi Development Authority has put this draft in the public domain and requested the public to put any suggestions or objections for MPD 2041.

This democratic approach is appreciable, authorities are welcoming the views, suggestions, or objections from the common public. Every state should follow this sort of approach to make the essence of democracy successful. *(The personal observation is the author’s view and does not intend to hurt anyone’s sentiment or feelings)*

¹ [https://dda.org.in/pdf/july13/Final%20MPD%202041%20-%20e%20Gazette %20English.pdf](https://dda.org.in/pdf/july13/Final%20MPD%202041%20-%20e%20Gazette%20English.pdf)